

Centennial of Benoit Mandelbrot's Birth

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Abstract

Fractals are non-Euclidean geometric figures, which have a fine structure and high similarity, and the pattern found in fractals is called self-similarity. They are easily found in nature, for example in plants and clouds. They are highly complex, requiring more advanced mathematics and sophisticated technological tools. From the middle of the 19th and 20th centuries onwards, it was realized that it was not possible to use Euclidean geometry to describe all of nature, hence the first announcements of this new non-Euclidean geometry. The term "fractal" was created in 1975 by Benoît Mandelbrot and in fact this year 2024 the centenary of his birth is celebrated.

Keywords: Mandelbrot; fractals; chaos; centenary.

MANDELBROT BRIEF BIOGRAPHY

According to MACTUTOR INDEX ⁽¹⁾, Benoît Mandelbrot was born in Warsaw, November 20, 1924, and died in Cambridge, October 14, 2010. He was a French mathematician of Jewish-Polish origin, with French and American nationality, who was notable for the development of a "roughness theory" and "self-similarity" of nature and in the field of fractal geometry.

Mandelbrot is known for his contributions to the field of fractal geometry, especially with regard to the so-called Mandelbrot set which consists of intricate, endless fractal shapes. The term "fractal" was coined by him in 1975. This notable character played the roles of mathematician, economist, scientist, writer, computer scientist, engineer, university professor. In 1958 he began a 35-year career at IBM. Because of his access to IBM computers, Mandelbrot ⁽¹⁾ was one of the first to use computer graphics to create and display fractal geometric images. In doing so, he was able to show how visual complexity can be created from simple rules. He used to say that things normally considered chaotic, like

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clouds, for example, actually have a certain degree of order. His research career included, in addition to mathematical physics, contributions to areas such as geology, medicine, cosmology, engineering and the social sciences.

INTRODUCTION

Mandelbrot ⁽²⁾ in the book *Fractals and Dynamics in Mathematics, Science and the Arts* says that from the middle of the 19th and 20th centuries onwards it was realized that it was not possible to use Euclidean geometry to describe all nature, hence the first announcements appeared of this new non-Euclidean geometry. Certain natural phenomena or objects that do not have a defined shape were seen as “mathematical monsters” or pathologies that challenged common notions of infinity. Transforming something like Galileo Galilei so vehemently defined, saying that the alphabet of nature was circles, triangles and other Euclidean figures, was a very significant change for the teaching of mathematics.

This gave rise to the first phenomena such as: Cantor dust, Peano curve, Koch curve, Sierpinski triangle, etc., each named after its creator. But it was only in 1975 that the use of the term fractal could be found when the Polish mathematician Benoit Mandelbrot made use of it for the first time, when he was about to complete his first major work on the subject, entitled “The Fractal Geometry of Nature”. It is worth mentioning that Mandelbrot did not create this geometry, he only named it, and is currently considered by many scientists to be the “Father” of Fractal Geometry, as he created the Mandelbrot Set, considered by mathematicians to be the most complex set in mathematics. It is interesting to mention that the definition of the word fractal comes from the Latin *fractus*, whose verb “*frangere*” corresponds to break, create irregular fragments.

In relation to the definition of fractal, Mandelbrot ⁽²⁾ explains that the real figure must resemble the geometric figure that constitutes the whole. Therefore, the idea of dimension given by Poincaré based on Euclidean foundations, in which a point has dimension 0, the straight line has dimension 1, the surface has dimension 2 and a portion in space has dimension 3 is now no longer accepted by fractals, because the dimension is fragmented, in which it satisfies non-integer and irrational numbers. Georg Cantor a mathematician of German origin stood out for presenting highly innovative ideas about the concept of infinity, he was also the formulator of set theory by proposing the construction of an object that ended up being called the Cantor set which plays an important role in fractal theory.

WHAT ARE THE FRACTALS?

According to NAVARRO ⁽³⁾ fractals are non-Euclidean geometric figures which have a fine structure and high similarity and the pattern found in fractals is called

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self-similarity. They are easily found in nature, for example in plants and clouds. They are little studied due to their complexity in studying them and requiring more advanced mathematics and expensive technological tools. Thus the fractals most covered in geometric training courses are, for example, the Cantor set, the Koch curve and the Sierpinski triangle, among others.

FUZZO ⁽⁴⁾ believes that the fractal arose from the need to calculate and describe certain natural phenomena or objects that do not have a defined shape. Fractals are geometric shapes that have patterns in their construction. It is possible to see that they are repeated infinitely on different scales, with each part of a fractal being similar to its whole. The pattern found in fractals is called self-similarity. There are several types of them and the main ones are geometric and random. Fractals are related to areas of physics and mathematics that are known as Dynamical Systems and Chaos Theory, as their equations are used to describe phenomena that, despite appearing random, in reality obey certain rules. Clouds, mountains, the circulatory system, coastlines or snow vases are examples of natural fractals.

The first fractals studied were the Cantor set, Koch snowflake and the Sierpinski triangle. There were also many other works related to these figures, but this science only managed to fully develop from the 1960s onwards, with the help of computing. Fractal geometry can be discussed through the fractals of Cantor, Koch, Sierpinski, Peano and Hilbert, describing the characteristics of self-similarity, scale and dimension (STEWART ⁽⁵⁾).

SIERPINSKI TRIANGLE ⁽⁵⁾

Figure1 Sierpinski triangle, an example of a fractal.

KOCH CURVES ⁽⁵⁾

Figure 2 Koch Curves

FRACTAL AND CHAOS

As HARRIS ⁽⁶⁾ and GLEICK ⁽⁸⁾ say currently fractals are part of the visual identity of chaos. As infinitely complex objects that are similar at all scales, they represent dynamic systems in all their glory. In fact, it turned out that the Lorenz attractor was a fractal, as are most strange attractors. And they are not limited to the representations of computers. The dimension of a fractal is a fractional value. Fractal geometry seeks organized patterns in seemingly random systems. Thus, fractal geometry is strongly linked to chaos, as both explore the complexity and unpredictability of nature.

LORENZ ATTRACTOR

The first fractal ^(6,7) to be considered was when Mandelbrot proved that the Lorenz attractor was a fractal. The Lorenz attractor was discovered in 1963, when meteorologist Edward Norton Lorenz studied a system of nonlinear differential equations and concluded that the possibility of meteorological prediction is limited by the very nature of the system. The Lorenz system of equations consists of a simplified model of the behavior of the atmosphere: it simulates the behavior of a fluid in a rectangular plane, whose temperature on the lower side is higher than that on the upper, generating convection currents.

MATHEMATICAL DEDUCTION ^(8,9)

This is the Lorenz system of equations:

$$dX/dt = s.(Y - X)$$

$$dY/dt = r.X - Y - X.Z$$

$$dZ/dt = X.Y - b.Z$$

It is a three-dimensional system, where

"X" represents convective flow; "Y" symbolizes the horizontal temperature distribution; "Z" denotes the vertical temperature distribution.

The three parameters that appear in the equations are

"s" represents the relationship between viscosity and thermal conductivity, or Prandtl number; "r" is proportional to the temperature difference between the lower and upper sides, or Rayleigh reduced number; "b" symbolizes the relationship between the height and width of the rectangle. In addition to being a three-dimensional system, the products X.Z and X.Y make it non-linear, necessary conditions for the existence of chaotic behavior.

The following figure schematizes the Lorenz attractor from two nearby initial points.

Figure 3 - Lorenz attractor in the XZ plane for initial values: (a) $X_0 = 0,0$; $Y_0 = 0,6$; $Z_0 = 0,0$; (b) $X_0 = 0,0$; $Y_0 = 0,6$; $Z_0 = 1,0$.

With a small variation of the initial data represented in Figure 3 (a) and (b) it is clear that the shape of the attractor is maintained, however, after a few iterations the trajectories become completely different. Because it was deduced from physical laws that govern the behavior of fluids, this simplified system can demonstrate the difficulty of making predictions for atmospheric activity. It is observed ^(8,9) that all systems in a chaotic regime with sensitivity to initial conditions become practically unpredictable as it is almost impossible under experimental conditions to determine the exact value of the initial conditions. Thus it can be seen that projected in the XZ plane as illustrated in Figure 3 the Lorenz attractor has a shape that resembles a butterfly.

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